

The breeding methods used by 31 rice breeders at 24 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian countries, 1975.

Breeding method	1st		2nd		3rd		4th		Users ^a	
	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%
Pedigree	21	68	3	10	3	10	2	6	29	94
Backcross	2	6	10	32	5	16	2	6	19	60
Bulk	1	3	9	29	5	16	0	0	15	48
Mutation ^b	0	0	3	10	4	13	5	16	12	39
Combination	6	19	3	10	5	16	4	13	18	58
Others	1	3	1	3	5	16	1	3	8	26
No indication	0	0	2	6	4	13	17	55	—	—

^aThe number and percentage of 31 breeders who indicated that they used each method as at least one of their breeding systems.

^bChemical, radiation, or natural.

Sixty-eight percent of the breeders (21) depended primarily on the pedigree method of breeding (see table); two breeders depended mostly on the backcross method, and one on the bulk method. Six breeders (19%) indicated that they depended primarily on a combination of breeding techniques.

Ninety-four percent of all breeders

surveyed used the pedigree system (in combination with other methods); 60% used the backcross method; and 48%, the bulk system.

Although none of the breeders depended primarily on mutation breeding (chemical, radiation, or natural) in their programs, 39% used mutation in combination with other methods.

ARC 11775 — an Assam rice cultivar that is promising for rainfed lowlands

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Kerala state grows 395,000 ha of monsoon rice. More than 80% of the area under autumn rice is sown in dry soil in mid-April during the premonsoon showers and later flooded as the southwest monsoon advances. Farmers dry sow the autumn rice so they can harvest it early and immediately transplant the winter rice, which depends on the meager and erratic northeast monsoon rains. The autumn rice crop is subjected to two major stresses: drought

during initial growth stages and weeds. A few semidwarf rices withstand some drought but they are more prone to smothering by weeds than are the local tall varieties. Farmers prefer tall, nonlodging rice with a lush canopy of leaves. But the present tall cultivars lodge, even before panicle emergence, and suffer severe yield losses.

Preliminary investigations indicated the adaptability for dry sowing of some elite International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) rices of intermediate stature.

Among the rices in the Assam Rice Collection, the accession ARC 11775 has been identified as drought tolerant, tall, nonlodging, and fertilizer responsive, with a high degree of blast resistance. Its seed-to-seed growth duration is 105 to 110 days vs. 130 to 135 days for the

Characteristics of ARC 11775 a promising cultivar for rainfed lowlands, and a tall local variety. Kerala, India.

Variety	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield (kg/day)	Kernel color
ARC 11775	106	2.5	26.6	White
Ptb 26 (local tall indica)	135	1.8	13.0	Red

most popular tall varieties (See table).

The yield per day of ARC 11775 is double that of the all local variety now grown. Earliness without yield loss is desirable for autumn rice so that popular winter rices can be transplanted earlier in rainfed paddies.

Suakoko 8 — a new rice variety recommended for iron-toxic swamps in Liberia

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Rice varieties with genetic tolerance to iron toxicity are considered useful in many inland valley swamps in Liberia, where symptoms of the disorder develop in most rice crops. Gissi 27, a local variety recommended for deep waterlogged swamps, is tolerant of iron toxicity. But being tall, photoperiod sensitive, and late maturing (165 – 170 days), it cannot be used for double-cropping or for high-technology rice cultivation. IR5 is recommended for inland valley swamps, but it is susceptible to iron toxicity, which reduces its yields by as much as 40%.

More than 3,000 rice varieties have been screened and tested during the past 4 years at the Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko. Emphasis has been on varietal tolerance for iron toxicity in inland swamps. The most significant result is the selection of the line 2526 (Siam 25/Malunja³), which is tolerant of iron toxicity and has been named Suakoko 8 by the Liberian Ministry of Agriculture.

In trials across the country during the past 3 years, Suakoko 8 outyielded IR5 by about 20% in iron-toxic swamps. Under nontoxic conditions, IR5 and Suakoko 8 yield similarly but farmers in various parts of Liberia prefer Suakoko 8 because it has better cooking quality and is more palatable.

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